

A comparative study of Nasugbu, Batangas beach resorts: Basis for crafting a marketing plan of RSAM Beach Resort and Pamana Beach Resort

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Abstract

Batangas is one of the most popular destinations near Metro Manila for a summer getaway. The province has many beaches and is famous for excellent diving spots. This research is focused on the comparison of two beach resorts in Nasugbu, Batangas in terms of the facilities, amenities, tourism services, price affordability, and promotion in order to provide a marketing plan for both resorts that will help promote and improve both establishments. The researchers used data from survey questionnaires answered by the customers of both resorts. The researchers conducted an interview with the management of both resorts and the local government unit of Batangas and from the ocular inspection. The researchers also gathered data from various related articles about the Philippine as a beach destination and also included factors to consider for a beach holiday and how small resort marketing as a basis for crafting marketing plan and destination profiling.

Keywords: Comparison; Marketing plan; Promotion.

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To cite this article:

Ylagan, G. B., Bueno, C. J., & Felizardo, M. T. (2021). A comparative study of Nasugbu, Batangas beach resorts: Basis for crafting a marketing plan of RSAM Beach Resort and Pamana Beach Resort. *SDCA Student Research Journal*, 10(1), 1-5.

Introduction

When the summer season takes over in the Philippines and the heat intensifies, it cannot be denied that most Filipinos would escape to the beach resorts. Philippines has a lot of renowned beaches and islands. With the Philippines consisting of more than 7,100 islands, one can hardly find a Filipino who is not fascinated with beaches. These beaches provide Filipinos with peace of mind and honest-to-goodness relaxation and relief from toxicity they have always been dreaming of. Also, Filipinos seem to enjoy the road trip and preparations that entail a beach outing. With the access to the social media, a lot of beautiful and previously unknown beaches are being discovered and are now being visited.

In planning for the summer adventure, Filipinos give importance to choosing destinations that are away from the hustle and bustle of the masses. They are not just looking forward for the unspoiled appearance of the beaches, but they also consider the distance of the location. The first location that would probably come to mind of most Filipinos is the summer playground closest to Manila, that is, Batangas. In particular, Nasugbu is known for its array of beaches with azure blue waters. Its proximity to the metropolis is one of the reasons of its popularity, but Nasugbu's beaches are already so well-known by themselves that the place makes a compelling case as a summer destination. Located about a hundred kilometers away from the metropolitan city, Manila, the coastal town of Nasugbu has perfected that balance between modest and modern lifestyle. Being the tourist hotspot in Batangas, Nasugbu is the closest getaway that is perfect for adventure and nature lovers.

However, amidst the pandemic season, travelers start to plan trips whenever availability is possible. As the protocols lifted, some business establishments are now open for operations with strict rules and guidelines to be followed. People should observe the quarantine protocol where the safety and security of everyone is the main priority. To provide guidelines or basis for choosing a resort that suits future travel in Nasugbu, Batangas, the researchers take on consideration the two beach resorts namely RSAM and Pamana Beach Resorts for a comparative study, especially that there is no comparative study being done yet pertaining to resorts attributes, which could be used as a basis for crafting a marketing plan beneficial for both resorts.

RSAM Beach Resort is located at Brgy. Calayo, Nasugbu, Batangas and it offers hospitable accommodations in the area. It offers an extensive view of the sea. It is popular because of its style which is neither American style nor design of accommodation and facilities that offers a great quality of stay in resort.

Pamana Beach Resort is the first and oldest resort in Brgy. Calayo, Nasugbu, Batangas. Pamana Beach Resort was born from the idea of having a slightly modern interior design with the touch of Filipino culture and values. It offers secluded and peaceful accommodation as they give priority to the security of their guest. This study will provide a marketing plan for both resorts to help them improve and promote their establishments for success in gaining more visitors.

A marketing plan prepares the company to anticipate and integrate in what the market does. A marketing plan plays an important role in being ready to deal with the changing conditions of the market. It is better to plan and prepare for a market change before it happens rather than finding out about it later on (Khemal, 2014). In the case of tourism studies, the comparative approach has been lengthily used for improving understanding of the subject, allowing researchers to gauge the significance, validity and reliability of the outcomes, both quantitatively and qualitatively.

The purpose of this study is to create a comparative study of RSAM Beach Resort and Pamana Beach Resort in Nasugbu, Batangas in terms of the facilities, amenities, tourism services, price affordability and promotion.

Methods

The researchers applied quantitative research to get data and information in relation to creating a marketing plan in terms of facilities, amenities, tourism services and promotion of the RSAM and Pamana beach resorts that are both located in Brgy. Calayo, Nasugbu, Batangas. Moreover, the research was supplemented by secondary data collected from host establishment websites, comments and reviews from third party sites such as Trip Advisor and Agoda, and inclusion of blog review by independent travelers. In this way the researchers would minimize the impact of limited sample size brought by current community quarantine.

The researchers used a separate respondent for each resort which has twenty-six (26) respondents each for both RSAM and Pamana beach resorts that lead to a total of fifty-two (52) participants. The material used to gather data was the questionnaire that includes survey questions pertaining to the objectives of the study. Survey questionnaire was distributed to the preferred respondents and gave a minute to answer the questions. Data were collected, tallied and calculated using Microsoft Excel. Results were interpreted through using the Likert Scale basis and tabular percentage form.

The research covered fifty-two (52) respondents that can rate their means of satisfaction based on their experience with the facilities, amenities and affordability of a resort in Nasugbu, Batangas specifically the RSAM beach resort and Pamana beach resort of Brgy. Calayo.

The study also used qualitative research. The sampling technique used in the study is the judgment or purposive sampling as the researchers required respondents who are familiar with the Rsam and Pamana Beach Resorts to do the comparison using the Likert scale survey based on their own opinion or experiences. This approach was used to have the tourists' insights regarding what to expect or meet their satisfactions, which will be useful for creating a feasible output plan for the research.

The variables of interest were measured using self-reports. The survey researchers asked the participants to answer directly from their own thoughts, experiences and feelings. This study used the Likert scale survey questionnaires as a source of collecting data for the study. The respondents measured their answers through rating, starting from extremely satisfied, very satisfied, moderately satisfied, up to the lowest rating which is not satisfied.

The researchers formulated survey questions that seek to solve the problem of the research. The instrument was validated by the faculty members from the School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management. To collect data, researchers used survey questionnaire and in-depth interview to identify the feelings and opinions of tourist regarding with the facilities and amenities of resort as well how it meets tourist satisfaction. The main advantage of this is that researchers can involve personal and direct contact for both respondents and researchers. Also, they can easily ask other questions during interviews to gather more data or information.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Comparative table of facilities and amenities between RSAM Beach Resort and Pamana Beach Resort

Criteria	RSAM		Pamana	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Rooms	3.38	Extremely Satisfied	2.84	Very Satisfied
Swimming Pool	2.62	Very Satisfied	3.38	Extremely Satisfied
Wi-Fi	3.26	Extremely Satisfied	3.26	Extremely Satisfied
Comfort Rooms	2.96	Very Satisfied	2.88	Very Satisfied
Reclining Chair	2.42	Moderately Satisfied	2.26	Moderately Satisfied
Safety Equipment	2.90	Moderately Satisfied	2.76	Very Satisfied
Restaurant	2.50	Moderately Satisfied	2.96	Very Satisfied
Cottages	3.15	Very Satisfied	2.90	Very Satisfied
Function Room / Hall	2.88	Very Satisfied	1.30	Not Satisfied

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 = Extremely Satisfied; 2.26 – 3.25 = Very Satisfied; 1.76 – 2.25 = Moderately Satisfied; 1.00 – 1.75 = Not Satisfied

Table 1 shows that tourists are extremely satisfied with the rooms as the facilities and amenities offered by RSAM Beach Resort, which shows the highest value of mean score of 3.38, followed by Wi-Fi with 3.26 mean score. Then tourists are very satisfied with the cottages (3.15), comfort rooms (2.96), function hall (2.88), and swimming pool (2.62).

On the other hand, tourists are moderately satisfied with the safety equipment (2.90), restaurant (2.50), and the reclining chairs with the lowest mean score of 2.42. According to the data gathered the product profile of RSAM Beach Resort in terms of facilities is in high demand from the tourists who visited there because majority of them are satisfied on the facilities because of its modern style. In terms of amenities, most of the tourists were not satisfied in terms of the absence of cottage, internet connection and restaurant inside the beach resort.

In terms of the facilities and amenities of Pamana Beach Resort, the swimming pool receives the highest value mean score of 3.38, which is extremely satisfied, followed by Wi-Fi, with 3.38 mean score. However, most tourists are very satisfied with the rooms, comfort rooms, safety equipment, restaurant, and cottages. On the other hand, the tourists are moderately satisfied with the reclining chair (2.26), and not satisfied with the function room / hall, which receives the lowest value of mean score of 1.30. According to the data gathered, the product profile of Pamana Beach Resort in terms of facilities states that all tourists who visited there is very satisfied during their stay because of the cozy place and ambience of the resort. On the other hand, in terms of amenities there is no function room built, but the tourists were very much satisfied on the complete amenities that this resort offers.

The distinguishable facility for RSAM is the rooms while Pamana is the swimming pool. Based on the gathered data, the distinguishable characteristic of RSAM Beach Resort is their rooms. Rooms are well-appointed, fully-renovated, furnished, and spacious. On the other hand, the other facilities and amenities are the common characteristics of RSAM Beach Resort. However, the distinguishable characteristic of Pamana Beach Resort is their swimming pool with numerous lights under the water which catches the eyes of the guests at night and contributes to the ambience of the resort while hearing the sound of the ocean waves.

Table 2. Comparative table of tourism services between RSAM Beach Resort and Pamana Beach Resort

Criteria	RSAM		Pamana	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Tour & Sightseeing / Attractions	3.00	Very Satisfied	2.92	Very Satisfied
Transportation	3.38	Extremely Satisfied	3.38	Extremely Satisfied
Activities	2.50	Moderately Satisfied	2.65	Very Satisfied
Visitor Information Center	2.96	Very Satisfied	2.80	Very Satisfied

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 = Extremely Satisfied; 2.26 – 3.25 = Very Satisfied; 1.76 – 2.25 = Moderately Satisfied; 1.00 – 1.75 = Not Satisfied

Table 2 shows that tourists are extremely satisfied with the transportation as the tourism service of RSAM Beach Resort, with the highest value mean score of 3.38. Then tourists are very satisfied with tour and sightseeing / attractions (3.00), and visitor information center (front desk) (2.96). However, tourists are moderately satisfied with the activities (indoor / outdoor), which got the lowest value mean score of 2.5 as the tourism service of RSAM Beach Resort. RSAM Beach Resort does not offer activities such as island hopping, however, in terms of visitor information center, it has more accommodating staffs.

Meanwhile, tourists are extremely satisfied with the transportation, which receives the highest value of mean score of 3.38. Then most tourists are very satisfied with the tours and sightseeing / attractions (2.92); visitor information center (front desk) (2.8), and activities (indoor / outdoor) with the lowest value of mean of 2.65. Pamana Beach Resort offers an island hopping in Loren Island. The staffs are accommodating and well-knowledgeable about the resorts' whereabouts; that is why the tourists are very satisfied in terms of tourism services.

Table 3. Comparative table of price affordability between RSAM Beach Resort and Pamana Beach Resort

Criteria	RSAM		Pamana	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Food & Beverage	2.50	Moderately Satisfied	2.69	Very Satisfied
Accommodation	3.38	Extremely Satisfied	3.00	Very Satisfied
Entrance Fee	2.96	Very Satisfied	2.65	Very Satisfied
Transportation Expenses	3.16	Very Satisfied	2.62	Very Satisfied

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 = Extremely Satisfied; 2.26 – 3.25 = Very Satisfied; 1.76 – 2.25 = Moderately Satisfied; 1.00 – 1.75 = Not Satisfied

Table 3 shows that tourists are extremely satisfied with accommodation as the most affordable price in RSAM Beach Resort, which got the highest value mean score of 3.38. Then tourists are very satisfied for both transportation expenses (3.16) and entrance fee (2.9), while tourists are moderately satisfied with the food and beverages, which got the lowest mean score of 2.50 as the least affordable price in RSAM Beach Resort. The Tourism Department assigns authority personnel, who monitors the tourists and collects all the environmental fees for the beach. Entrance fee makes access in pool and beach is a bit expensive but has a cheaper price of accommodations. But some of the tourists are not satisfied about the entrance fee of the resort because it only offers a simple and small kind of swimming pool which is not enough to accommodate big group size of visitors.

Meanwhile, tourists are very satisfied with the accommodation, which got the highest value of mean score of 3.00, followed by the food and beverages (2.69), entrance fee (2.65), and transportation expenses with the lowest value mean score of 2.62. Tourists in Pamana Beach Resort are very satisfied with the entrance fee for pool and beach because it has a big infinity type of pool and has a reclining chairs for tourists to relax, unlike RSAM Beach Resort which does not have. The Tourism Department also assigns authority personnel, who monitors the tourists and collects all the environmental fees for the beach.

Table 4. Comparative table of promotion between RSAM Beach Resort and Pamana Beach Resort

Criteria	RSAM		Pamana	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Blog	1.73	Not Satisfied	1.30	Not Satisfied
Facebook	2.42	Moderately Satisfied	3.38	Extremely Satisfied
YouTube	2.11	Moderately Satisfied	2.50	Moderately Satisfied
Instagram	1.76	Moderately Satisfied	1.26	Not Satisfied
Flyers	1.50	Not Satisfied	1.80	Moderately Satisfied
Tv / Ads	1.57	Not Satisfied	1.23	Not Satisfied
Word of mouth	2.96	Very Satisfied	2.76	Very Satisfied

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 = Extremely Satisfied; 2.26 – 3.25 = Very Satisfied; 1.76 – 2.25 = Moderately Satisfied; 1.00 – 1.75 = Not Satisfied

Table 4 shows that the highest value of mean in RSAM Beach Resort in terms of promotion is the Word of Mouth, which has a mean of 2.96, categorized as very satisfied, followed by Facebook, 2.42; YouTube, 2.11; and Instagram, 1.76. It also uses social media platforms as promotion such as Facebook and Twitter. Aside from the social media, they also depend on the good service feedback from the guests because they believe that word of mouth is their major way to promote.

On the other hand, tourists are extremely satisfied with Facebook as promotion of Pamana Beach Resort, with the highest value mean score of 3.38; and very satisfied with the word of mouth with 2.76 mean score. However, tourists are moderately satisfied with YouTube (2.5), and flyers (1.80), and not satisfied with blogs (1.3), Instagram (1.26), flyers (1.80), and TV / ads with the lowest mean score of 1.23. Pamana Beach Resort also use social media platform as promotion such as Facebook and Instagram accounts. They also depend on the good service feedback from the guests because they believe that Word of mouth is their major way to promote. The result stated that both resorts' key source of promotion is through word of mouth of their customers or guests suggesting to other people to visit the resorts.

Table 5. Summary of the market position of RSAM and Pamana Beach Resorts

Areas of Consideration	RSAM Beach Resort	Pamana Beach Resort
Tourism Services	Very Satisfied	Very Satisfied
Price Affordability	Very Satisfied	Very Satisfied
Promotion	Moderately Satisfied	Moderately Satisfied
Management Perceived Value Proposition based on Interview	Mid-Ranged Beach Resort Affordable Quality Accommodation Quality Event Location Customer Service	Mid-Ranged Beach Resort Affordable Good Location and Ambiance Good for Family Get-together Price Discount
Customers' Perceived Value Proposition based on Consumer Online Forum	Affordable Quality Accommodation Customer Service	Good Location and Ambiance Price Discount
Distinguishable Resort Facilities	Rooms	Swimming Pool

RSAM Beach Resort is classified as mid-ranged resort according to the Local Government Unit of Brgy. Calayo, Nasugbu, Batangas. It is a family-owned business establishment for many years and based on the results, relative market position of RSAM beach resort is identified as a perfect location to host an event due to its spacious function hall and multiple number of rooms to stay with the modern type of resort. On the third-party review, it is considered to have a secured area, friendly and accommodating staff.

Pamana Beach Resort is also classified as mid-ranged traditional Filipino resort. It has a peaceful vibe, a perfect place to have a getaway with the family because it is near Metro Manila, where the ambiance of the rooms and facilities has a touch of Filipino culture that could be appreciated by many guests. On the third-party review, Pamana Beach Resort is small but provides an excellent service, good discounts, and clean and neat environment.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the gathered data on survey questionnaire checklist, management interview, and data analysis from the third-party platforms such as Expedia, Agoda and Booking.com's comments and review of consumers, it concludes that there is a slightly difference between RSAM Beach Resort and Pamana Beach Resort. The facilities and amenities, tourism services, and price affordability of RSAM Beach Resort have more impact in terms of guest's preferences, comments, and reviews to its consumers which makes it slightly different to Pamana Beach Resort. On the other hand, Pamana Beach Resort stabilized its way of promotion rather than RSAM Beach Resort.

After a thorough review and careful analysis of the data, the following recommendations are offered by the researchers. First, both resorts should undergo a seminar or training that would help the management to improve the strategic ways of selling products and services, and the quality and services of both resorts should be consistent, improved, and if possible be upgraded to attract new clients, especially in selling rooms. This should be done through consistent distribution of resort services by creating a social media platforms with the use of ads management strategy to boost people's engagement towards the resort.

Also, the researchers recommend that the management of RSAM and Pamana beach resorts should develop marketing tools such as tarpaulins and posters for promotion because the researchers observe that upon arriving in Brgy. Calayo, there are not enough posters or any signages referring to the beach resorts. Also, they should use the power of social media because nowadays almost everyone has his / her own social media accounts, and this can be a big help to promote both resorts. Since the researchers found out there are existing accounts of RSAM Beach Resort and Pamana Beach Resort in social media particularly in Facebook and Instagram, the researchers highly recommends maintaining their social media accounts active, updated, and responsive.

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